

Extreme Light Infrastructure ERIC

Data Policy

As adopted by the Extreme Light Infrastructure ERIC General Assembly on 17 March 2022.

Introduction

The Extreme Light Infrastructure (ELI) is the world's largest and most advanced high-power laser research infrastructure and a global technology and innovation leader in high-power, high-intensity, and short-pulsed laser systems. As the first international laser research infrastructure dedicated to science and research applications of ultra-intense and ultra-short laser pulses, ELI will provide high quality access to the international research community for prospective applications in medicine, radiography, fusion energy, environment, materials sciences, nanotechnologies, and biochemistry.

Emerging from a coordinated effort of a multi-national scientific laser community, ELI is the first large-scale research infrastructure located in the Central Eastern European Member States. In 2006, ELI was recognised by the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) as a strategic priority for Europe and included on the ESFRI Roadmap as a Landmark project. For the construction, ELI has employed an innovative funding model combining European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) and co-funding from the hosting countries for construction.

In 2021, the Extreme Light Infrastructure (ELI) was granted the legal status of European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) by the European Commission. The ELI ERIC is currently participated by Members (Czech Republic, Hungary, Italy and Lithuania) and Observers (Germany and Bulgaria), and is responsible for making the ELI facilities available to the scientific community as a single international organisation, with unified governance and management. The ELI ERIC consists of two facilities hosting operational world-class high-power, high-repetition-rate laser systems, specialised in different fields of research: ELI-Beamlines in Dolní Břežany (Czech Republic), which also hosts the ERIC statutory seat, and the ELI-ALPS for Attosecond Physics in Szeged (Hungary). The forthcoming third facility ELI-NP for Nuclear Physics is under construction in Măgurele (Romania) and expected to complement the current ELI ERIC facilities in the future.

For a research infrastructure entering into operations such as ELI ERIC, there is an expectation from both users and funding agencies that experimental data will be made available and comply with the FAIR principles. In this context, the data policy, is a key component of the research data management framework, addressing several critical issues that organise the relation with visiting users and the user community in general when it comes to data (ownership, embargo, access to data, storage, curation, etc.). It is also an internal driver pushing ELI to understand data as a service and leverage the value of experimental data. Naturally, this perspective has a direct impact on technological choices made around data management, technological choices which will further define the evolution of the ELI ERIC Scientific Computing and Data Management System (SCDMS).

Data Policy

This Data Policy governs the management of and access to data relevant to perform and calibrate experiments as well as from experiments performed at the Extreme Light Infrastructure ERIC (ELI ERIC). It pertains to the curation, storage and access to data and metadata collected from the operation and scientific usage of the ELI Facilities.

Scope

This Data Policy applies to all measurements performed for and during the experiments for which beamtime at the ELI Facilities has been granted, in accordance with the ELI ERIC Access Policy and confirmed in a User Access Agreement. That includes, but is not limited to, raw data, metadata and the associated auxiliary data collected and derived from scientific experiments and laser/beamlines operations at the ELI Facilities operated by ELI ERIC (hereinafter referred to as 'Data'). Authors' rights are subject to the ELI ERIC Intellectual Property Rights Policy. Acceptance of the Data Policy and terms and conditions derived from it shall be a condition for the awarding of beamtime.

Basis

This policy has regard for the following guiding documents:

- Article 13(2) of the ELI ERIC Statutes, according to which *“Open Access to FAIR data sets and metadata stored in Open Access repositories shall be favoured for data collected as a result of the use of the ELI Facilities ...”*;
- [Directive \(EU\) 2019/1024](#) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information.
- The [“Turning FAIR data into reality” report](#) by the European Commission’s FAIR Expert Group, which outlines guiding principles to make data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable;
- The [European Data Strategy](#), which recognises the European Open Science Cloud (EOSCA) as the nucleus for a science, research and innovation data space;

Principles

The ELI ERIC considers research data to be valuable results of its operation which contributes to sharing and dissemination of knowledge across the European Research Area. Results of publicly-supported research should in principle be made publicly available. The ELI ERIC aims to preserve and manage Data according to the 'FAIR' principles, meaning that Data shall be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and organised in Reusable datasets. Data shall be managed according to processes and standards having regard, among others, to security, quality control, data tracking and documentation.

For experiments performed at the ELI facilities, a Data Management Plan (DMP) will be provided by the users applying for experiments. The DMP is the core document used to define the experimental data lifecycle and will be updated as needed and possible during the experiment.

ELI ERIC data shall receive a unique and persistent identifier (Digital Object Identifier). Users shall be able to cite the persistent identifier in any publication that refers to the data (or to a

subset of the data). Machine-readable metadata standards shall be preferred for describing the datasets and associated services.

A rich metadata format shall be used and associated with the datasets, providing detailed provenance information. The metadata format shall meet the domain-relevant community standards and be described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes. Metadata shall be registered/indexed into a common searchable resource making the data and metadata easily searchable and discoverable by the users.

Objectives

For the purposes of this policy, ELI ERIC aims to fulfil the following objectives:

- Prepare data for the exclusive use of the scientists who conducted the experiment which produced the data for up to three years after the conclusion of the experiment;
- Develop tools for FAIR-by-design metadata collection and storage. Collaborate with users for the production of adequate metadata to all successfully generated datasets.
- Preserve data for a minimum of 10 years for scrutiny, comparison and reproducibility to reinforce scientific knowledge and integrity;
- Promote data use, after an embargo period, for other scientists in the same field or for cross-disciplinary research and machine learning;
- Enable researchers to mine ELI public data and metadata and in previously unknown ways or apply future methods to existing data.

Responsibilities and reporting

The ELI ERIC shall be the custodian of the Data, with the responsibility to collect, secure, archive and provide access to the Data. The ELI ERIC Director General (DG) determines and implements relevant data management and access-related processes and procedures as part of the ELI ERIC management system. The DG may delegate this responsibility. The DG will report to the General Assembly annually on the application of this Data Policy.

The specific management procedures, rules and guidelines, following from and consistent with this policy, shall constitute the body of internal regulations determining and limiting all activity relative to data management and data access carried out by ELI ERIC.

ELI ERIC shall have a Scientific Data Management plan, which is a defined strategy covering the production of data, volumes, metadata requirements, data retention periods, data disposal, processing and analysis requirements and tools, thus clarifying all aspects of data management. The SDM plan shall be reviewed and updated periodically, at least every second year, evolving with the computing environment.

The ELI ERIC organisation shall adopt a 'Code of Conduct for Research Integrity and Ethics' based on *The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity ALLEA (All European Academies)*. That code shall consider principles of *Reliability, Honesty, Respect and Accountability*. This Data Policy and any further version adopted by the ELI ERIC GA shall be citable using a persistent identifier.